

Deliverable D7.4

Publication of the Synthesis of the contest ideas

Photo and video contest

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Abstract

The activity, initially planned as a literary or rhetorical contest, was transformed into an Audiovisual contest, thinking of encouraging the participation of young people from UNITA Universities.

Thus, 120 photos and videos were presented on the idea of European citizenship and European values that were examined by a jury of specialists from the six UNITA Universities.

The transformation of the activity gave rise to a slight delay, as a consequence of the need to prepare a call that adequately detailed the technical requirements for the presentation of the photos and videos.

Synthesis report of the photo and video contest

The UNITA project previews the organization of a contest on the meaning of the European Citizenship for the promotion of this concept among the students of the UNITA Universities.

In its original version this activity was conceived as a literary or rhetorical contest. However, the WP7 Task Force members took account to the fact that there are already previewed, and held, other activities for students consisting in the submission of texts, such as the Prizes for Bachelors and Masters dissertations.

Considering this fact, after a debate the WP7 Task Force decided to propose to the Management Committee a different approach for this contest. According with this new format this activity would take the form of an audiovisual contest, including two categories of prizes for each UNITA University, one prize for photos and another one for videos. The students of UNITA Universities would send their photos and videos reflecting on the best way possible on the idea of European Citizenship and European values.

This change was approved by the Management Committee and the call with this format was launched for the six UNITA Universities on 3 March, 2022, giving to the candidates the opportunity to submit their photos and videos until 31 March. The total number of candidates, in the six UNITA Universities, reached 120 in both categories.

The dates referred show a slight deviation in the development of the activity according to the original project due to the change of the nature of the contest and because of technical questions related with the preparation of the call, such as the format for the submission of photos and videos.

Once the deadline for the submission of photos and videos was over the works were examined by a Jury composed by a specialist of each UNITA University. The members of the Jury were:

- Elodie Kredens (Université Savoie Mont Blanc)
- Maria Paola Pierini (Università degli Studi di Torino).
- Silvia Martí Marí (Universidad de Zaragoza).
- Madalin Marienut and Ciprian Hord (Universitatea de Vest din Timisoara).
- Richard Lacroix (Université de Pau et des Pays de l'Adour).
- Ana Catarina dos Santos Pereira (Universidade da Beira Interior).

After the examination of all the photos and videos sent to the different UNITA Universities the winners are, classified by University and category:

	Photo	Video
UPPA	Ambre Darpheuil	Lola Grandvuiet
USMB	Frammenti Chagnard	Morgane Mazon
UNITO	Annalisa Racca	Zoe Schuster

	Photo	Video
UVT	Ioana Oniciu	Darius Gabriel Doronbatu
UBI	Lia Mota	Solange Rachado
UNIZAR	Izarbe Ríos Asín	Uxue Calderón

The winning photos and videos have been sent to the WP8 of the UNITA Alliance for their dissemination, including their uploading onto the UNITA webpage.

This report represents the deliverable of this activity and includes the references to the development of the contest and the final results, having the winning photos and videos at the UNITA webpage as it has been said before.

The delay in the submission of this report according with the original calendar is due, as it has also been said, to the change decided for the contest, modifying it to become an Audiovisual contest in order to have a different approach to the dissemination of the European Citizenship that could be positive for enhancing the participation of our students. This change obliged the organisers to include in the call some technical questions that were outside their expertise field, consequently the help of specialists was required and some additional weeks were necessary for preparing the call in the best possible way.

Annexe: Rules of the contest

The rules of the contest in its English version are included below as an annex. These rules were published in all the languages of the UNITA Universities, including them on the UNITA website and on the respective websites of each University.

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CONTEST RULES OF UNITA PHOTO & VIDEO CONTEST– UNITA *UNI-VERSITAS MONTIUM* PROJECT

The name UNITA evokes the commitment of six universities (Università degli studi di Torino, Universidad de Zaragoza, Université Savoie-Mont Blanc, Universitatea de Vest din Timișoara, Universidade da Beira Interior y Université de Pau et des Pays de l'Adour) and the new four Associated Partner Universities: Università degli studi di Brescia, Instituto Politécnico da Guarda, Universidad Pública de Navarra and Universitatea Transilvania Brașov to a closer integration of their academic, research and general activities.

The UNITA photo and video competition offers to UNITA university members and associated universities the possibility to share experiences and visions of European identity and citizenship.

All UNITA members and associated universities are encouraged to submit entries. Registration for the competition is free of charge.

THEME

The goal of this contest is to find visual expressions of the European project of cooperation, mainly about the concepts of European Identity and Citizenship. The candidates must catch in their photos or videos the essence of this concepts, reflecting them in their different manifestations and/or showing the new realities transforming the lives of European citizens.

For more information on the subject, consult the website of the UNITA Alliance in the section *Our values, vision and mission* (<http://univ-unita.eu/>).

ELEGIBILITY

The Photo & Video Contest is open to UNITA students, teaching staff, researchers, and administrative/services staff, as well as students, teaching staff, researchers and administrative/services staff from the new associated universities. Photographs and videos must have been taken or produced by the person submitting the work, must be original and must not have been previously exhibited or taken part in any other competition.

PRIZES

The prizes will be awarded by a jury of experts. The jury's decision will be final and the authors will be informed by e-mail.

The works will be selected by the jury on the basis of artistic relevance and their connection to the theme of European Integration and Identity.

One winner per university will be selected in each category. UNITA will showcase photographs and videos in several marketing initiatives, such as the UNITA Office, websites, social media, advertisements, the electronic bulletin of each university, e-newsletters, programme brochures, exhibitions, etc.

The winning entries will be awarded € 215 for each category (photo & video). The prizes will be paid for by the UNITA Budget at the six UNITA Universities and by their own budgets at the new Associated Universities.

PHOTO CONTEST GUIDELINES (Modality I)

Submission Guidelines:

Photographs must be sent to one of the following e-mail addresses, depending on the university they want to take part in:

Universidad de Zaragoza (UNIZAR) and the new Associated Partner Universidad Pública de Navarra (UPNA) must be sent to: unitacontact@unizar.es

Università degli studi di Torino (UNITO) and Università degli studi di Brescia must be sent to: unita.communication@unito.it

Universidade da Beira Interior (UBI) and Instituto Politécnico da Guarda must be sent to: unita@ubi.pt

Université de Pau et des Pays de L'Adour (UPPA) must be sent to: unita@univ-pau.fr

Université Savoie Mont Blanc (USMB) must be sent to: unita.office@univ-smb.fr

Universitatea de Vest din Timișoara (UVT) and Universitatea Transilvania Brașov must be sent to: unita@e-uvt.ro

Each participant may only present a maximum of one piece of work in each Modality.

In the text of your email, you must include the following:

- Your full name
- Location of the image
- Brief sentence by the artist stating that the photo is an original piece of work and the fruit of his/her own work.
- You will also need to include this declaration in the body of your email:
"I _____(type your full name here)_____ give permission for UNITA to use my photographs for promotional purposes in print and web materials."

Deadline for submissions: 21th March 2022. Entries received after the deadline or deemed inappropriate will not be considered.

Photographs:

Single Image competition or Photographic Essay / Series of photographs (Maximum 7 images related to each other)

For either option (Single or Series) the technical requirements for the images are the same.

- File format: JPEG
- Maximum file size: 10 MB
- Longest side length: 2000 px
- File resolution: 72 dpi
- The file should be renamed (for SINGLE IMAGE): university_surname_first name_title of the photograph.jpeg...for example: unizar_smith_mary_my photo title.jpeg
- The file should be renamed (for SERIES): university_surname_first name_title01.jpeg... university_surname_first name_title02.jpeg... etc.

VIDEO CONTEST GUIDELINES (Modality II)

All submissions must be digital. Please upload your submission through Google Drive and share it with the UNITA Office depending on the university you want to take part in by sending an e-mail:

Universidad de Zaragoza (UNIZAR) and the new Associated Partner Universidad Pública de Navarra (UPNA) must be sent to: unitacontact@unizar.es

Università degli studi di Torino (UNITO) and Università degli studi di Brescia must be sent to: unita.communication@unito.it

Universidade da Beira Interior (UBI) and Instituto Politécnico da Guarda must be sent to: unita@ubi.pt

Université de Pau et des Pays de L'Adour (UPPA) must be sent to: unita@univ-pau.fr

Université Savoie Mont Blanc (USMB) must be sent to: unita.office@univ-smb.fr

Universitatea de Vest din Timișoara (UVT) and Universitatea Transilvania Brașov must be sent to: unita@e-uvt.ro

In the text of your email, you must include the following:

- Your full name
- The title of your video
- Google Drive link to your video
- Where the video took place
- A sentence or two about yourself
- Brief sentence by the artist stating that the video is an original piece of work and the fruit of his/her own work.
- You will also need to include this declaration in the body of your email:
“I ____ (type your full name here)____ give permission for UNITA to use my video for promotional purposes in print and web materials.”

Submission deadline: 21th March 2022.

Works received after the deadline or deemed inappropriate will not be considered.

Videos:

Every participant is allowed to upload 1 video. Videos can feature actors or actresses, can be narrative, documentary or animation, black and white or color with or without sound.

- The file should be renamed: University_Last name_Title.mp4
- Movie file format: .mp4 (video file format converter to .mp4 > cloudconverter.com [1])
- Final image format: landscape
- Image resolution: Full HD 1920 x 1080
- Maximum length of the film: 1 minute
- Maximum file size: 2 GB
- All videos that include text, monologues or dialogue must include subtitles in English.

IMPORTANT COPYRIGHT INFORMATION

Please be sure to use open source music and photographs any time the work is not your own and to credit the original producer. Photographs or video footage of identifiable individuals should have written consent of the implied individuals to appear on it. Movies should not contain copyright material (for example the soundtrack; audio materials from free digital libraries, such as archive.org, may be used to avoid this).

Participants should be over 18 years old and must be the sole copyright owners of the short movie or photos.

Disclaimer

UNITA assumes no responsibility for submissions that are incorrect, damaged, destroyed, lost, late, incomplete, illegible, altered or misdirected. UNITA also assumes no responsibility for any damage or loss resulting from or related to the video contest. By submitting photos/videos for this contest, participants declare they understand all of the rules and regulations of the competition.

By entering the contest you certify that any photos/videos submitted are of your authorship and that you own the rights to distribute them. You certify that these photos/videos do not belong to someone else and are not protected by any copyright. You acknowledge that individual(s) who appear in the photographs have provided permission to be included.

You grant UNITA permission to reproduce any submitted images for the purposes of publicity, marketing, and communications.

Participants will be responsible for any claims from third parties in relation to image rights or any other rights derived from the intellectual property law applicable.